

RAPID CARBON FIBRE SURFACE PLASMA TREATMENT FOR ENHANCED FIBRE-THERMOPLASTIC INTERFACIAL PERFORMANCE

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CONTENT

- 1. Fibre-thermoplastic interface**
- 2. Atmospheric air plasma treatment**
- 3. Morphology, functionality and strength**
- 4. Conclusions**

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Motivation – Fibre reinforced thermoplastics

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[1] Mengjin, W. U., et al. (2021). Interfacial performance of high-performance fiber-reinforced composites improved by cold plasma treatment: A review. [Online]: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2021.101077>

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Motivation – Fibre reinforced thermoplastics

Waste polymer matrix

Fibre Interphase

Can a single fibre surface treatment improve bonding with multiple thermoplastics?

Load transferred from weak matrix to strong and stiff fibres through interphase

Weak fibre-matrix interfacial strength limits thermoplastic composite performance¹

Coatings

- Solvents - environmental concern
- Matrix specific - e.g. PA6 only

→ **Plasma surface modification process**

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[2] GlobalSpec (2020) How to recycle polymer waste. [Online]: <https://insights.globalspec.com/article/14792/how-to-recycle-polymer-waste>

Motivation – Atmospheric pressure plasma jet treatment

[1] Becker, Kurt H., et al. (2004), eds. *Non-equilibrium air plasmas at atmospheric pressure*. CRC press.

[2] Lu, X., et al. (2016). Reactive species in non-equilibrium atmospheric-pressure plasmas: Generation, transport, and biological effects. *Physics Reports* 630. – Online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physrep.2016.03.003>

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Continuous plasma treatment

Continuous plasma treatment

Surface modification - Morphology

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Carbon fibre size

Carbon fibre size – SEM

Carbon fibre size – Nitrogen atmosphere TGA

Roughened plasma treated surface – SEM

Carbon fibre

As-received

2 μm

Carbonized PAN
precursor tracks

Roughened plasma treated surface – SEM

Carbon fibre

Carbonized PAN
precursor tracks

Roughened plasma treated surface – SEM

Increasing nozzle-fibre distance →

All treated for 1 second

Roughened plasma treated surface – AFM

Tilt and curvature corrected

As-received, $S_q = 22$ nm

Roughened plasma treated surface – AFM

Tilt and curvature corrected

As-received, $S_q = 22$ nm

Desized, $S_q = 20.82$ nm

$d = 10$ mm, $t = 1$ s, $S_q = 34.9$ nm

2D PSD interpretation with SEM image – As-received

As-received, Sq = 22 nm

2D PSD interpretation with SEM image – Plasma treated

$d = 10 \text{ mm}, t = 1 \text{ s}, S_q = 34.9 \text{ nm}$

Surface modification - Functionalisation

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Surface modification – Transmission KBr FT-IR

Surface modification – Transmission KBr FT-IR

Expected functionality

Carboxylic acid

Ketone

Peroxy acid

Aldehyde

... no surprises.

Surface modification – Short beam strength

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Short beam strength - method

ASTM D2344

$$\sigma_{SBS} = 0.75 \times \frac{P_m}{b \times h}$$

P_m Maximum force

b Width

h Thickness

Short beam strength – failure mode

ASTM D2344

$$\sigma_{SBS} = 0.75 \times \frac{P_m}{b \times h}$$

P_m Maximum force

b Width

h Thickness

Failure mode

Short beam strength - results

Method benefits

1. High-speed treatment with affordable equipment
2. Improved SBS for CF/PA6 and CF/PP

Unresolved problems

1. Non-uniformly roughened fibre-surface
2. Negligible effect on CF-polyester interfacial strength

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